

Motivation

Context

- Fast growth of the need for **Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs)** on **embedded** devices with **limited resources**,
- Required exploration flow to identify **optimized implementations**.

Challenge

- On **multi-core platforms**, **concurrent accesses to shared resources** surge the latency and are hard to model,
- Other approaches fail to properly evaluate the **impact of communications** on timing for a large scale of architectures.

Objective

- Propose a **hybrid modeling flow** to enable fast and accurate **performance prediction** for **ANNs on Multi-Processor Systems on Chip (MPSoCs)**.

Contribution

Figure: Schematic of the proposed modeling environment to enable performance prediction of ANNs on MPSoC

Modeling environment

- Extension of the environment proposed in previous work to ANNs,
- Proposition of an **analytical computation time model calibrated through measurement**, used in a **SystemC simulation**,
- **Exploration** of several partitionings and mappings of ANNs under **timing constraints** using the modeling flow

Case study

- **Fully-connected ANNs** (also called multi-layer perceptrons) trained using the MNIST and the GTSRB data-sets,
- ANNs are described using the **deep learning framework LibFANN** and modeled using **Synchronous DataFlow (SDF)**,
- Targeted architectures consist of a **shared memory and several tiles** composed of 1 processing element with local memory.

Validation

- Validation of the modeling flow by **comparing timing predictions with real measurements** for several partitionings and mappings of **three fully-connected ANNs** on multi-core architectures implemented on **two different FPGAs**,
- The observed **accuracy** of the modeling flow is **99,5%** on average on 21 different scenarios, with **highest error of 2,28%**.

Figure: Exploration of several partitionings and mappings for two different ANNs and identification of optimized solution for each number of tiles (highlighted in red)

Prospects

- Proposition and integration of a **power model** in the modeling environment to enable **exploration under timing and energy constraints**,
- Extension of the flow to **other classes of ANNs** such as **Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs)**.